

BLENDED LEARNING APPROACH FOR ENHANCEMENT OF EPP LEARNING SKILLS AMONG GRADE 5 STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

The study aimed to determine the enhancement of the skills of grade 5 pupils in blended learning. The study was conducted using a quasi-experimental design through questionnaires and pre-post-test, administered to the pupils of Del Remedio Elementary School. The independent variables were the blended learning with two modalities: the modular and online, while the dependent variables are the learning skills, which are pre-test and post-test. Data was collected and analyzed. The statistical treatments used were mean score, mean difference, t-value, and standard deviation. The mean score increase in critical thinking compared with the pre-test mean scores in the modular approach. The t-value of creativity is .866, collaborative is 1.720, and lastly the critical thinking with 2.927. After all, the p-value is significant at .01 level. Based on the findings and conclusion of the researcher, the following recommendations are suggested: School principal conducted a seminar and trainings in EPP teachers about enhancing the creativity and collaborative skill of the pupils that suited in the kind of learning approach or modalities; Teachers give instructional video about the topic to enhance the skills of the pupils; Teachers may explore the use of contextualized learning to other subjects or fields of discipline since the study proved that students' critical thinking skills were enhanced upon exposure to contextualized learning; Students may do a daily journal of their learning experiences in EPP which can help them to improve the skills in creativity and collaborative since the study shows that most of the students'

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